

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Table S1. Mapping of original discipline labels in MAG to nine broader disciplines in Social Sciences, according to OECD Fields of Science (OECD, 2015)

Remapped discipline label	Original L1 label in MAG
Psychology	applied psychology, clinical psychology, cognitive psychology, developmental psychology, psychoanalysis, psychotherapist, social psychology,
Economics & Business	accounting, advertising, business administration, classical economics, commerce, development economics, econometrics, economic history, economic policy, economic system, economy, environmental economics, finance, financial economics, financial system, industrial organization, international economics, international trade, keynesian economics, labour economics, law and economics, macroeconomics, management, market economy, marketing, mathematical economics, microeconomics, monetary economics, neoclassical economics, political economy, positive economics, public economics, socioeconomics, welfare economics
Educational science	mathematics education, medical education, pedagogy
Sociology	gender studies, anthropology, ethnology, demography
Law	law, criminology
Political Science	public administration, public relations
Social & Economic Geography	economic geography, environmental planning, environmental protection, environmental ethics
Media & Communications	communication, library science, media studies
Other social sciences	social science

Table S2. Summary for publications studying temporal trends of interdisciplinarity

Source	Data & Classification Scheme	Measurement	Discipline/Region	Period	Main Results
Porter and Rafols, 2009	<i>Data:</i> Web of Science Sampling 1000 articles on average for each categories and year (1975, 1985, 1995, and 2005) <i>Classification Scheme:</i> Web of Science subject category	Disciplinary diversity in reference; Rao-Stirling index;	Six research field from STEM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biotechnology & Applied Microbiology • Engineering, Electrical & Electronic • Mathematics • Medicine – Research & Experimental • Neurosciences • Physics – Atomic, Molecular & Chemical 	1975-2005	“Modest increase (mostly around 5% growth);” (p. 719) “Science is indeed becoming more interdisciplinary, but in small steps.” (p. 719)
Levitt et al. 2011	<i>Data:</i> Web of Science <i>Classification Scheme:</i> Web of Science subject category	Percentage of cross-disciplinary citing documents (PCDCD)	Social Sciences and its subfields	1980-2000	Decrease in the 1980s, sharp rise in the 1990s.
Chang & Huang, 2012	<i>Data:</i> SSCI, Thomson Reuters 1,536 articles published in 10 journals from LIS <i>Classification Scheme:</i> Library of Congress classification (LCC)	Disciplinary diversity in reference and author affiliation; Brillouin index;	Library and Information Science (LIS)	1978-2007	“The degree of LIS interdisciplinarity increased between 1978 and 2007.” (p. 28)
Raj Kumar Pan et al., 2012	<i>Data:</i> All published articles in Physical Review journals <i>Classification Scheme:</i> Physics and Astronomy Classification Scheme (PACS)	Interconnections between its subfields; Average number of links per code and average link weight, new links from dissimilar branches of the hierarchy;	Physics	1985–2009	“Steady increase, indicating increased connectivity between different subfields of physics;” (p. 7) “increase in interdisciplinarity between the subfields of physics, as dissimilar branches of the PACS hierarchy are becoming increasingly connected;” (p. 3)
Lužar et al., 2014	<i>Data:</i> SICRIS national database (Slovenia) <i>Classification Scheme:</i> SICRIS field labels for researcher	Disciplinary diversity within communities of collaboration network; Proposed new measurement;	Slovenia	1960-2010	Modest increase in 1970s and 1980s, minor decrease in 1985 to 1990, and remain stable afterwards. “The frequency of interdisciplinary research is only proportional with the overall growth of the network.” (p. 1)
Larivière & Gingras, 2014	<i>Data:</i> Web of Science <i>Classification Scheme:</i>	References to journals in a different discipline	General Science	1900-2010	Increase since the mid-1980s

	Web of Science subject category				
Chen et al., 2015	<i>Data:</i> Web of Science 1,539,526 publications in the field of BMB <i>Classification Scheme:</i> Web of Science subject category	Disciplinary diversity in reference; Rao-Stirling index;	Biochemistry and Molecular Biology (BMB)	1910-2010	“Doubles over the century with a 32% increase during 1975-2005”; (p. 1315) “The rise in interdisciplinarity is stronger in BMB than in the six disciplines which Porter and Rafols investigated.” (p. 1315)
Karlovčec & Mladenić, 2015	<i>Data:</i> SICRIS national database and COBISS national bibliographic database (Slovenia) <i>Classification Scheme:</i> SICRIS field labels for researcher	Disciplinary diversity of collaboration network; Proposed new measurement, an extension of Stirling’s diversity index;	Slovenia	1996-2013	Increasing trend.
Craven et al., 2019	<i>Data:</i> Web of Science 97,945 articles related to biodiversity <i>Classification Scheme:</i> Web of Science subject category Extracted terms from the title and abstract, via a continuous dynamic topic model (LDA-cDTM)	Concept diversity and subdiscipline diversity; “ species richness and the effective number of species for the probability of interspecific encounter...(1/Simpson's index)” (p.6747)	Biodiversity Science	1990-2012	“either stable or declining concept or subdiscipline diversity” (p.6752)
Gates et al., 2019	<i>Data:</i> Web of Science 19,252,639 publications <i>Classification Scheme:</i> Web of Science subject category	Disciplinary diversity in reference; Rao-Stirling index;	General Science	1900-2017	Increasing. “ a typical article is inspired by and impacts three times more disciplines this decade than it did 50 years ago.” (p. 34)

Table S3. Results for matching experiments with different bin size decisions (bin size = 10, 20)

	<i>Before matching</i>	<i>After matching Bin size = 10</i>	<i>After matching Bin size = 20</i>
<i>Economics and Business</i>	3.2 %	2.7 %	2.4 %
<i>Educational sciences</i>	4.8 %	3.3 %	2.0 %
<i>Law</i>	1.4 %	1.4 %	3.5 %
<i>Media and communications</i>	1.3 %	0.3 %	- 0.2 %
<i>Other social sciences</i>	3.1 %	1.0 %	1.3 %
<i>Political science</i>	3.4 %	1.7 %	1.3 %
<i>Sociology</i>	2.0 %	0.6 %	0.1 %
<i>psychology</i>	2.3 %	2.1 %	1.7 %

Results for data validation tasks

Task 1: Is MAG assigning more discipline labels to recent publications than older ones, which could nullify the discovered increasing trends in variety by claiming the observed increase is an artefact of the dataset?

Figure A1 shows the distribution of average number of L1 labels for referenced publications investigated in this study. It indicates that publications published in recent years are indeed assigned more L1 labels than those in earlier periods. But the level of difference (increase) is minor and not substantial enough to overturn our findings.

Figure S4. Average number of discipline labels (L1) for investigated references.

Task 2: Are some disciplines relatively new and did they therefore not appear in the earlier periods?

All 60 disciplines involved in this study are present throughout our selected time span. Here we present two disciplines as a case study, namely gender studies (rise in prominence around 1990s) and media studies (first M.A. program around 1975). In Figure A2, we can see that both of them have been present in our dataset since the 1960s, although only occupying a small proportion of publications in the beginning.

Figure S5. Temporal trends of publications share for two research domains.